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“THE STRENGTH BEHIND THE STORM”

I grew up in a house patched together with tin and bamboo. When it rained, we each scrambled for a spot where water didn't drip through. My mother would laugh off the state of our door, saying, “No one would ever rob this place. One look and they'll know there's nothing to take.”

Still, that house was home. It was filled with love, even though it wasn't filled with comfort. My father was a drunkard, and our family knew more chaos than calm. But we stayed together. We laughed. We survived.

From a young age, I learned what hardship looked like. It wasn't romantic, it was real. My mother worked hard, and I helped in my own way. In kindergarten, I was already selling boiled bananas and homemade camote chips to my classmates. Some of them mocked me. They said the chips were too hard. I remember one of them sneering, “These don't even taste good.” What they didn't see was my mother staying up late the night before, slicing the camote carefully, frying it, packing it, all for a few pesos to keep us going. I never told her about the teasing. She was already carrying enough.

Sometimes, I'd come home with snacks I couldn't sell. I could see the disappointment in her eyes. So, to spare her, I made them my snacks. I learned early on, being poor doesn't give anyone the right to laugh at you. And just because your father drinks don't mean your whole family should be dismissed.

That's when I decided I wanted to be a teacher. Because teachers were respected. People called them “ma'am.” And maybe, just maybe, if I became one, people would respect us too. It wasn't just about dignity, it was about survival.

High school didn't make things easier. I kept selling, this time, eggplants. One day, someone caught sight of me carrying them and smirked. That look cut deep. But these were the kinds of moments that challenged me. The kind that shaped me. They made me promise to myself that if I ever rose above this life, I wouldn't forget what it felt like to be at the bottom.

In third year, high school, my father died from organ failure. We were devastated. We had nothing. But my mother, she stood up and became both father and mother to us. She carried us through our most vulnerable time.

One moment that stayed with me happened on my birthday in fourth year. Our adviser made me sit in front of the class while they sang to me. Then she said, “*Agbasa ka nalaing, ta tulungam tu ni mamang mo. Haan*

mu sayangen ti banbannug na ken saksakripisyo na. Kayam eta.” Study hard so you can help your mom. Don’t waste her sacrifices. You can do it.

That encouragement pierced straight through me. Outside of my mother, few people believed in me. And in that moment, I knew, I wanted to be that kind of teacher. Someone who believes in kids others ignore. But college? That still felt impossible.

Then my mother told me something I’ll never forget: *“Ipuatak ti batug ku nga langit ken daga.”* I’ll stake everything, heaven and earth, just to send you to college.

That night, I cried. I couldn’t believe it. She took me to Aparri for the entrance exam herself. She didn’t want me to be a teacher, she was afraid I wouldn’t pass the board exam. And to be honest, I was scared too. But I had no backup plan. I wanted to teach. I wanted to rise.

Throughout college, we did whatever we could to survive. We husked corn under the scorching sun. We harvested banana shoots by the river and sold them. We climbed trees, made coconut oil, bottled it, and sold it. We woke up early to harvest string beans and carried sacks across rivers, barefoot, soaked, and exhausted.

My mother would laugh, saying I was getting stocky from all the lifting, but I could carry more than most. She was tired. But she never broke. And because she stayed strong, I stayed strong.

I graduated with my bachelor’s degree, with no delays.

Then, just when we thought we were catching our breath, Typhoon Lawin hit. It destroyed our small farm. It tore down our home. The roof was gone, walls collapsed. And yet, our house was only marked “partially damaged.” Why? Because apparently, it had always looked that way.

That hit me hard. Even before the storm, our home wasn’t considered a real home.

We had to stay with relatives. I saw the weariness on my mother’s face, and I felt it in my bones. But it made me fight harder. I wasn’t just chasing my dream anymore; I was chasing our survival.

In early 2017, I met someone who pointed me toward Apayao State College. That was the next step. I took it.

Now, I help my mother earn a living. We’re still not there, but we’re far from where we started. My mother sleeps peacefully now, without worries about debt or rain dripping on her bed. For me, that’s more than success. That’s peace.

The road here wasn’t easy. There were times I wanted to give up. But I’ve learned that life doesn’t have to be easy, it just has to be meaningful.

The darker it gets, the more you crave the light. Learn to value the darkness. Let it teach you. Let it mold you. If there’s anything I’ve learned, it’s this, define your dreams. Be clear. Know what you want. Because if you don’t, you’ll be easily swayed. The only time you get distracted is when you take your eyes off your goal.

And to those raising dreamers, parents, guardians, support them. Walk with them. Believe in them. Especially when they fail.

Because the person who dreams, no matter how many storms they face, will find the courage to rise again. And maybe, one day, they'll look back and realize that every drop of rain, every bag of corn, every coconut oil bottle, every laugh, every tear, was worth it. Because they made it.

